

Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reactions of 2,4,6,8-tetra-bromo-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine

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Abstract : Tetrarilated 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine were prepared by Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reactions of the corresponding 2,4,6,8-tetra-bromo-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine in good yields.

Keywords : Catalysis, palladium, Suzuki-Miyaura reaction.

Introduction

Suzuki-Miyaura coupling is widely used in organic synthesis to create carbon-carbon bonds it has become one of the most versatile synthetic methods in organic synthesis¹. The easy availability of boron reagents, broad functional group tolerance, and general applicability of the reaction contributed to its increasing importance in both academic research and industrial production². The palladium catalyzed reaction can be conducted by using a wide variety of phosphine ligands in the presence of suitable bases such as carbonates, hydroxides, phosphates, or alkoxides. A base is needed to accelerate the transmetallation step of the catalytic cycle. Brominated and iodinated aromatic compounds are favored over chlorinated counterparts due to lower reactivity of the C-Cl bond in the oxidative addition step. A generally accepted reactivity order is I > OTf > Br > Cl^{4,5}.

Many 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine derivatives have pharmacological and biological activities such as antiallergic, antihistaminic, antiemetic, antiepileptic and anti-inflammatory activity, as well as spasmolytic, serotonin antagonistic, sedative and as antifungal⁶. And other derivatives have been used successfully as drugs for examples chlorimipramine is a clinically effective tricyclic antidepressant which is also used in the treatment of obsessive and phobic states. Imipramine and desimipramine also used as antidepressants⁷.

There are several classical efficient synthetic routes available for the synthesis of the tricyclic moiety. Thiele and Holzinger⁸ prepared 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine for the first time in 1899. Kitamura and coworkers⁹ prepared the 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine derivatives from the reactions between substituted 2-nitrobenzaldehyde with substituted 2-nitrobenzyl-phosphonic acid esters to give dinitrosystems which were subsequently reduced to afford the diamino derivatives and after heating to around 300 °C in the presence of different catalysts to give the substituted 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine. Gailliot and Roberts¹⁰ have suggested the possibility of ring closing *N*-substituted *o*-amino-*o*-chlorobenzyls under Goldberg conditions using copper powder as catalyst. Bergmann *et al.*¹¹ reported the intramolecular coupling of *N*-acetyl-2,2-di(bromomethyl)-diphenylamine by using phenyllithium. The 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine undergo possible direct substitution reactions e.g. nitration¹², bromination¹³, Friedel-Crafts acylation and formylation¹⁴.

Here I report a new and convenient synthesis of arylated 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine by Suzuki-Miyaura cross-coupling reactions of the 2,4,6,8-tetra-bromo-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine.

The products reported herein are not readily available by other methods.

Fig. 1. The tricyclic antidepressant compounds.

Results and discussion

Bromination of commercially available 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[*b,f*]azepine **1** provides selectively 2,4,6,8-tetra-bromo-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[*b,f*]azepine **2** in very high yield by using 2.4 equivalent of Br₂ in acetic acid at room temperature for 1 h¹⁵.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of **2**. Conditions : i, **1** (1.0 equiv), Br₂ (4.0 equiv.), AcOH at r.t.

The Suzuki-Miyaura reaction of **2** with 4.0 equiv. of various arylboronic acids **3** afforded the 2,4,6,8-tetraaryl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[*b,f*]azepine **4a-j** in 72–84% yields (Scheme 2, Table 1). The reaction had to be carried out at higher temperature (130 °C). Very good yield were obtained for products derived from both electron

Scheme 2. Synthesis of **4a-j**. Conditions : i, **2** (1.0 equiv.), **3a-j** (1.0 equiv.), K₂CO₃ (2 M, 1 mL), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (12 mol %), THF, 120 °C, 4 h.

Table 1. Synthesis of **4a-j**

3,4	Ar	4 (%) ^a
a	4-MeC ₆ H ₄	79
b	3-MeC ₆ H ₄	77
c	3,5-MeC ₆ H ₃	76
d	4-(MeO)C ₆ H ₄	84
e	4-EtC ₆ H ₄	79
f	4-FC ₆ H ₄	75
g	4-CF ₃ C ₆ H ₄	77
h	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	73
i	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	72
j	C ₆ H ₅	80

^aYields of isolated products.

poor and rich arylboronic acids. All attempts to induce a site-selective reaction of **2** failed. The reaction of **2** with 2.0 equivalents of arylboronic acids resulted in the formation of complex mixtures.

In conclusion, I report for the first time the synthesis of 2,4,6,8-tetraaryl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[*b,f*]azepine which are not readily available by other methods.

Experimental

General procedure for Suzuki-Miyaura reactions :

A solution of **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), K₂CO₃ (2 M, 1.0 mL), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (12 mol%) and of arylboronic acid **3** (4.0 equiv.) in THF (4 mL) was stirred at 130 °C for 4 h under argon atmosphere. In the reaction mixture H₂O (20 mL) and CH₂Cl₂ (25 mL) were added at 20 °C. The organic and the aqueous layers were separated and the latter was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (20 mL × 2). The combined organic layers were dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and the filtrate was concentrated in vacuum. The residue was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, heptanes/EtOAc).

2,4,6,8-Tetra-*p*-tolyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[*b,f*]azepine (**4a**) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 4-methylphenylboronic acid **3a** (80 mg, 0.588 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K₂CO₃ (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4a** was isolated as a white solid (65 mg, 79%); m.p. 56–58 °C. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.27 (12H, s, 4CH₃), 3.20 (4H, s, 2CH₂), 6.67 (1H,

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br s, NH), 6.86 (4H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH), 6.93 (4H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.05 (2H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, ArH), 7.10 (4H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.20 (2H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.36 (4H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, ArH); ¹³C NMR (62.9 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 21.0, 21.2 (CH₃), 36.0 (CH₂), 126.2, 127.0, 127.9, 129.2, 129.2, 129.3 (CH), 129.4, 131.2, 131.3, 135.6, 136.0, 136.6, 137.7, 138.5 (C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3366 (m), 3019 (w), 2916 (m), 2851, 2728, 1902, 1788 (w), 1599 (s), 1567 (w), 1497, 1452, 1432 (s), 1390 (w), 1357, 1324, 1303 (s), 1250, 1218, 1205, 1182 (w), 1106 (m), 1067, 1035, 1019, 954 (w), 887 (m), 810 (s), 788, 771 (w), 752, 719 (m), 694, 647, 615, 573, 540 (w); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* (%) = 556 ([M+H]⁺, 48), 555 ([M]⁺, 100), 554 (9), 465 (6), 451 (15), 435 (16), 394 (10), 302 (30); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for C₄₂H₃₇N [M]⁺ : 555.29205, found 555.291479.

2,4,6,8-Tetra-m-tolyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4b) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 3-methylphenylboronic acid **3b** (80 mg, 0.588 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K₂CO₃ (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4b** was isolated as a white solid (63 mg, 77%), m.p. 62–64 °C. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.14 (6H, s, 2CH₃), 2.28 (6H, s, 2CH₃), 3.20 (4H, s, 2CH₂), 6.67 (1H, br s, NH), 6.82–6.94 (8H, m, ArH), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz, ArH), 7.07 (2H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, ArH), 7.13–7.19 (2H, m, ArH), 7.22 (2H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.27 (4H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (75.4 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 21.4, 21.5 (CH₃), 35.4 (CH₂), 123.5, 126.3, 126.8, 127.2, 127.2, 128.3, 128.6 (CH), 129.0 (C), 129.4, 129.9 (CH), 131.4, 131.5, 138.1, 138.2, 138.6, 138.6, 140.6 (C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3364 (m), 3206, 3020, 2915, 2848, 2729, 1939 (w), 1601 (s), 1583 (w), 1504, 1484, 1451, 1429 (s), 1386, 1357, 1323, 1315, 1305 (m), 1256, 1227, 1167, 1108, 1093, 1036, 963 (w), 906 (m), 876 (s), 829 (w), 780 (s), 751, 743, 729 (w), 699 (s), 623, 609, 584, 543 (w); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* (%) = 556 ([M+H]⁺, 42), 555 ([M]⁺, 100), 554 (9), 465 (17); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for C₄₂H₃₇N [M]⁺ : 555.292502, found 555.292502.

2,4,6,8-Tetrakis(3,5-dimethylphenyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4c) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 3,5-dimethylphenylboronic acid **3c** (88 mg, 0.588 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₄

(20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K₂CO₃ (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4c** was isolated as a white solid (68 mg, 76%), m.p. 217–219 °C. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 2.11 (12H, s, 4CH₃), 2.25 (12H, s, 4CH₃), 3.20 (4H, s, 2CH₂), 6.66–6.68 (6H, m, ArH), 6.71 (1H, br s, NH), 6.81 (2H, br s, ArH), 7.05 (2H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.09 (4H, br s, ArH), 7.20 (2H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, ArH); ¹³C NMR (75.4 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 21.3, 21.4 (CH₃), 36.1 (CH₂), 124.3, 127.0, 127.0, 128.0, 128.1, 129.0 (CH), 129.1, 131.3, 131.4, 137.9, 138.0, 138.5, 140.6 (C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3357 (s), 3015, 2949 (w), 1917 (m), 2850, 2726 (w), 1598 (s), 1556, 1537 (w), 1495 (s), 1461 (m), 1446 (s), 1417, 1389, 1363 (m), 1326, 1311, 1301 (w), 1290, 1284, 1266 (m), 1237, 1210, 1185, 1163, 1126, 1120, 1095 (w), 1034 (m), 996, 963, 904 (w), 877 (m), 860 (w), 839 (s), 767, 746, 734 (m), 718 (w), 709, 701, 693 (s), 670 (w), 650 (m), 634 (w), 601 (m), 582, 554, 540, 528 (w); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* (%) = 612 ([M+H]⁺, 10), 611 ([M]⁺, 100), 610 (7); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for C₄₆H₄₅N [M]⁺ : 611.35465, found 611.356504.

2,4,6,8-Tetrakis(4-methoxyphenyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4d) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 4-methoxyphenylboronic acid **3d** (89 mg, 0.588 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₄ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K₂CO₃ (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4d** was isolated as a white solid (76 mg, 84%), m.p. 160–162 °C. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 3.18 (4H, br s, 2CH₂), 3.72 (6H, s, 2OCH₃), 3.74 (6H, s, 2OCH₃), 6.60 (4H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, ArH), 6.75 (1H, br s, NH), 6.82 (4H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, ArH), 6.95 (4H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, ArH), 7.02 (2H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.16 (2H, d, *J* 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.38 (4H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, ArH); ¹³C NMR (62.9 MHz, CDCl₃) δ : 36.0 (CH₂), 54.9, 55.3 (OCH₃), 114.1, 114.1, 126.9, 127.4, 127.7 (CH), 129.2 (C), 130.5 (CH), 130.7, 130.8, 133.2, 138.4, 158.5, 158.7 (C); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 3343 (m), 3070, 3031, 2996, 2954, 2930, 2834 (w), 1604 (s), 1573 (w), 1498, 1454, 1432 (s), 1393 (w), 1362, 1327, 1281 (m), 1241, 1173 (s), 1106 (m), 1066 (w), 1027 (s), 955, 887, 850 (w), 828, 813 (s), 788, 770, 753, 726, 641, 614, 589 (w), 572 (m); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : *m/z* (%) = 620 ([M+H]⁺, 40), 619 ([M]⁺, 100), 604 (11), 310 (9);

HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for $C_{42}H_{37}NO_4$ $[M]^+$: 619.27171, found 619.27234.

2,4,6,8-Tetrakis(4-ethylphenyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4e) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 4-ethylphenylboronic acid **3e** (88 mg, 0.588 mmol), $Pd(PPh_3)_4$ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K_2CO_3 (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4e** was isolated as a white solid (71 mg, 79%), m.p. 205–207 °C. 1H NMR (250 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 1.13–1.21 (12H, m, 4CH₃), 2.51–2.61 (8H, m, 4CH₂), 3.21 (4H, s, 2CH₂), 6.68 (1H, brs, NH), 6.88 (4H, d, J 8.0 Hz, ArH), 6.98 (4H, d, J 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.06 (2H, d, J 2.1 Hz, ArH), 7.12 (4H, d, J 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.20 (2H, d, J 2.1 Hz, ArH), 7.38 (4H, d, J 8.0 Hz, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (62.9 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 14.2, 14.5 (CH₃), 28.4, 28.5, 36.2 (CH₂), 125.3, 126.1, 126.9, 127.0, 127.1, 128.2 (CH), 128.6, 130.1, 130.3, 134.9, 136.9, 137.4, 141.4, 141.8 (C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) ν : 3368 (m), 3202, 3080, 3020 (w), 2960, 2927 (m), 2869, 2244, 1904, 1783, 1666 (w), 1603 (m), 1565 (m), 1497, 1452, 1433 (s), 1407, 1391 (w), 1357, 1323, 1305 (m), 1260, 1252, 1184, 1105, 1060, 1048, 955 (w), 906, 888 (m), 860 (w), 825 (s), 771, 753 (w), 730 (s), 647, 616, 580 (w); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 612 ($[M+H]^+$, 46), 611 ($[M]^+$, 100), 610 (9), 596 (8), 291 (10); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for $C_{46}H_{45}N$ $[M]^+$: 611.35465, found 611.355807.

2,4,6,8-Tetrakis(4-fluorophenyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4f) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 4-fluorophenylboronic acid **3f** (82 mg, 0.588 mmol), $Pd(PPh_3)_4$ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K_2CO_3 (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4f** was isolated as a white solid (64 mg, 77%), m.p. 184–185 °C. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 3.19 (4H, s, 2CH₂), 6.38 (br s, NH), 6.77–6.83 (4H, m, ArH), 6.94–7.01 (10H, m, ArH), 7.17 (2H, d, J 2.0 Hz, ArH), 7.37–7.42 (4H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (62.9 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 34.8 (CH₂), 115.4 (d, J 21.4 Hz), 115.8 (d, J 21.4 Hz), 125.9, 126.8 (d, J 8.0 Hz), 127.4 (CH), 128.5, 129.1, 129.8 (C), 130.1 (d, J 8.0 Hz) (CH), 133.2 (d, J 3.2 Hz), 135.4 (d, J 3.2 Hz), 137.5 (C), 161.0 (d, J_{CF} 245.5 Hz, (CF)), 161.2 (d, J_{CF} 245.5 Hz, (CF)); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) ν : 3379 (s), 3063, 3037, 2942, 2915, 2850, 1888 (w), 1601 (s), 1499, 1454, 1432 (s),

1403, 1388 (w), 1361, 1325, 1314, 1295 (m), 1269 (w), 1217, 1155 (s), 1105, 1088, 1069 (w), 1013, 953 (m), 937, 902, 892, 882, 857 (w), 830 (s), 785 (m), 763 (w), 753, 725, 646 (m), 610, 584 (w), 569, 553, 545 (m); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 572 ($[M+H]^+$, 43), 571 ($[M]^+$, 100), 556 (7); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for $C_{38}H_{25}F_4N$ $[M]^+$: 571.19176, found 571.193024.

2,4,6,8-Tetrakis(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4g) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 4-trifluoromethylboronic acid **3g** (112 mg, 0.588 mmol), $Pd(PPh_3)_4$ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K_2CO_3 (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4g** was isolated as a white solid (87 mg, 77%), m.p. 205–207 °C. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 3.25 (4H, s, 2CH₂), 6.23 (1H, s, NH), 7.04 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.17 (4H, d, J 8.2 Hz, ArH), 7.30 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.37 (4H, d, J 8.3 Hz, ArH), 7.54 (8H, s, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (75.47 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 35.9 (CH₂), 120.2 (q, J_{CF} 270.9 Hz, CF₃), 120.7 (q, J_{CF} 270.9 Hz, CF₃), 125.6 (d, J_{CF} 3.7 Hz, CH), 125.8 (d, J_{CF} 3.7 Hz, CH), 126.5, 127.2 (CH), 128.1 (d, J 32.2 Hz), 129.4 (d, J 32.2 Hz) (C), 129.7 (CH), 130.1, 130.3, 130.7, 138.7, 141.9, 143.5 (C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) ν : 3379 (s), 3063, 3037, 2942, 2915, 2850, 1888 (w), 1601, 1499, 1454, 1432 (s), 1403, 1388 (w), 1361, 1325, 1314, 1295 (m), 1269 (w), 1217, 1155 (s), 1105, 1088, 1069 (w), 1013, 953 (m), 937, 902, 892, 882, 857 (w), 830 (s), 785 (m), 763, 753, 725, 646 (m), 610, 584 (w), 569, 553, 545 (m); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 772 ($[M+H]^+$, 7), 771 ($[M]^+$, 37), 770 (100), 627 (5); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for $C_{42}H_{25}F_{12}N$ $[M]^+$: 771.17899, found 771.178786.

2,4,6,8-Tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4h) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 4-chlorophenylboronic acid **3h** (92 mg, 0.588 mmol), $Pd(PPh_3)_4$ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K_2CO_3 (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4h** was isolated as a white solid (71 mg, 73%), m.p. 205–207 °C. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ : 3.18 (4H, s, 2CH₂), 6.32 (1H, s, NH), 6.92 (4H, d, J 8.5 Hz, ArH), 6.97 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.10 (4H, d, J 8.5 Hz, ArH), 7.18 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.24 (4H, d, J 8.5 Hz, ArH), 7.36 (4H, d, J 8.5

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Hz, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (62.9 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 35.8 (CH_2), 126.7, 127.5, 128.5, 128.8, 129.0 (CH), 129.7, 130.2 (C), 130.6 (CH), 132.6, 134.0, 136.6, 138.6, 138.7 (C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) ν : 3374 (m), 3025, 2915, 2846, 1900, 1778, 1599 (w), 1509, 1488, 1451, 1431 (s), 1394, 1383 (w), 1357, 1323 (m), 1297, 1247 (w), 1214 (m), 1191, 1176, 1120 (w), 1088, 1011 (s), 954 (w), 905, 890 (s), 860 (w), 819 (s), 801, 753 (m), 728 (s), 693, 681, 649, 611, 571, 542 (w); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 641 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], 12), 639 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], 50), 637 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], 100), 635 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], 74); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{25}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}$ ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl]) : 641.06471, found 641.066599; calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{25}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}$ ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl]) : 639.06766, found 639.068357; calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{25}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}$ ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl]) : 637.07061, found 637.070270.

2,4,6,8-Tetrakis(3-chlorophenyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4i) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), 3-chlorophenylboronic acid **3i** (92 mg, 0.588 mmol), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K_2CO_3 (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4i** was isolated as a white solid (68 mg, 72%), m.p. 205–207 °C. ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.20 (4H, s, 2CH_2), 6.37 (1H, br s, NH), 6.92–6.96 (2H, m, ArH), 7.00 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.05 (3H, br s, ArH), 7.08–7.13 (3H, m, ArH), 7.16–7.24 (6H, m, ArH), 7.31–7.34 (2H, m, ArH), 7.43–7.44 (2H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (62.9 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 124.4, 126.4, 126.6, 126.8, 127.4, 128.1, 128.7, 129.4 (CH), 129.7 (C), 129.9, 130.0 (CH), 130.4, 134.6, 134.7, 138.7, 139.9, 142.0 (C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) ν : 3375 (s), 3207, 3058, 3021, 2916, 2562, 2247, 1939, 1873, 1766, 1693 (w), 1591, 1561, 1505 (s), 1474 (w), 1453, 1429 (s), 1406, 1384, 1355, 1322, 1311 (m), 1290, 1259, 1215, 1190, 1164, 1114 (w), 1096, 1078 (m), 1036 (w), 996, 961 (m), 904, 871 (s), 842 (w), 778 (s), 756 (m), 730, 701, 689 (s), 648, 631, 618, 606, 568, 541 (w); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 641 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], 9), 639 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], 45), 637 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], 100), 635 ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], 70); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for

$\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{25}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}$ ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl]) : 641.06471, found 641.066599; calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{25}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}$ ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl], ^{37}Cl]) : 639.06766, found 639.068357; calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{25}\text{Cl}_4\text{N}$ ($[\text{M}]^+$, ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{35}Cl], ^{37}Cl]) : 637.07061, found 637.070270.

2,4,6,8-Tetraphenyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo[b,f]azepine (4j) :

Starting with **2** (75 mg, 0.147 mmol), phenylboronic acid **3j** (72 mg, 0.588 mmol), $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (20 mg, 12 mol%, 0.0176 mmol), K_2CO_3 (2 M, 1.0 mL), and THF (4 mL), **4j** was isolated as a white solid (58 mg, 80%), m.p. 180–182 °C. ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 3.22 (4H, s, 2CH_2), 6.61 (1H, s, NH), 7.02–7.08 (12H, m, ArH), 7.16–7.20 (2H, m, ArH), 7.23 (2H, d, J 2.2 Hz, ArH), 7.26–7.31 (4H, m, ArH), 7.45–7.48 (4H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (75.47 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 36.1 (CH_2), 126.4, 126.5, 127.3, 127.4, 128.3, 128.7, 128.8, 129.2 (CH), 129.6, 131.3, 131.5, 138.5, 138.6, 140.5 (C); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) ν : 3381, 3360, 3077, 3077, 3054, 3024, 2929, 2844 (w), 1599 (m), 1573, 1556 (w), 1512, 1493, 1456, 1441, 1428 (s), 1403 (m), 1357, 1325 (s), 1308 (m), 1273, 1250, 1212, 1189, 1179, 1155, 1108, 1072, 1027, 1000, 953, 902, 892 (w), 882 (s), 855, 845, 804, 775 (w), 756, 694 (s), 660, 643, 610 (w), 574, 538 (m); GC-MS (EI, 70 eV) : m/z (%) = 500 ($[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 37), 499 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 100), 498 (12), 484 (7), 249 (11); HRMS (EI, 70 eV) : calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{29}\text{N}$ $[\text{M}]^+$: 499.22945, found 499.229638.

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